

Guide to Implementation

1. Outline clear goals and objectives

- Identify and describe the peculiarities of the museum type:
 - o Type A – high-density and innovative museum
 - o Type B – natural history and scientific museum
 - o Type C – widespread art gallery
 - o Type D – sites museums with tangible and intangible heritage and landscapes
 - o Type E – historical palaces, labelled as museums, including UNESCO sites
 - o Type F – demo-ethnic-anthropological museums, including rural culture museums, anthropological museums and museums of art and popular traditions.
- Describe the initial situation
- Describe the chosen technologies to be implemented
- Identify specific challenges and opportunities
- Consider the potential effects on the involved stakeholders (e.g., museums, local public bodies)

2. Describe knowledge sharing among project participants

- Illustrate the training activities for the staff of the winning companies (e.g., seminars, workshops)
- Explain the exchange of knowledge by the winning companies regarding how the chosen technologies work and how to use them

3. Describe how the guidelines and prototypes identified (in WP3) have been used (or not)

- Detail the digitalisation processes
- Illustrate User interface (UI) and user experience (UX) design
- Outline software programming design
- Pinpoint what has not been used and explain why

4. Outline the introduction of the technology to museum staff or other involved stakeholders (e.g., local public bodies, tour guides)

- Training on use and maintenance
- Describe opportunities and objectives
- Familiarise staff with technology through training sessions and workshops on self-guided learning
- Collect staff feedback

5. Describe the experimentation session

- Evaluate with real users to track of the effectiveness and appropriateness of the proposed solutions
- Identify strengths and weaknesses (possibly using a SWOT analysis)
- Explain how the proposed solutions can foster citizens participation, accessibility, and social inclusion

6. Conclusions

- Identify technological gaps
- Describe any unforeseen issues that arose during the implementation
- Delineate further lines of research